

Supplementary Material

Used_Oil_Survey

Open Survey on the Use and Disposal of Cooking Oils and Grease in Restaurants

This survey is part of a research project by the University of Guadalajara aimed at understanding common practices in the management of used cooking oils and grease in restaurant kitchens, cafés, diners, and food stalls. The objective is to better understand how these residues are handled in everyday practice and some related factors.

This survey is directed at people who work, have worked, or are familiar with the operations of kitchens in food establishments, regardless of their size. Responses are completely anonymous, and your experience or knowledge is highly valuable to this study.

If you have experience or knowledge in more than one establishment, please respond based on the one where you have worked or have the most knowledge about oil or grease management in the kitchen. Thank you for your participation.

1. What is your age range?

- 16–24 years
- 25–39 years
- 40–54 years
- 55 years or older
- Prefer not to say

2. What is your gender identity?

- Woman
- Man
- Prefer not to answer

3. What type of establishment have you worked in, currently work in, or are familiar with its kitchen operations?

- Restaurant
- Fast food restaurant (e.g., McDonald's, KFC, Pollo Pepe, etc.)
- Café
- Diner / small local eatery
- Street food stand
- Other

4. Which of the following best describes your situation regarding kitchen work and the management of oil or grease waste?

(Select one option.)

- I currently work in a kitchen and know how oil or grease waste is handled
- I worked in a kitchen and know how this waste is managed
- I have not worked directly in a kitchen, but I know how this waste is handled
- I have no experience or knowledge on this topic

5. In which municipality is (or was) the establishment located where you work(ed) or know its kitchen operations?

- Guadalajara
- Zapopan
- Another municipality in the Metropolitan Area of Guadalajara
- Another municipality in Jalisco different from the above
- A state other than Jalisco

6. Did you receive any instruction or training on how to manage oil or grease waste in the kitchen of the establishment you know or where you worked/work?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know / Don't remember

7. Was there any device or metal/plastic box under the sink to retain grease in the kitchen? (Some places use grease traps to prevent oil and grease from reaching the drain.)

- Yes
- No
- I don't know / Didn't know what it was

8. How was oil or grease waste disposed of in the place where you work(ed) or know its operations?

(You may select multiple options if applicable.)

- Stored in containers for collection
- Left to cool and thrown in the trash
- Poured directly down the drain
- Not handled properly
- I don't know / Don't remember

9. Do you know if an external company collected the used oil or cleaned the grease trap in the establishment?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

10. How many times was the frying oil reused before being discarded?

- Only once
- 2 to 3 times
- Until it changed color/texture
- It was not reused
- I don't know

11. Approximately how many liters of used oil were generated per week at the place where you work(ed) or know its operations?

- Less than 5 liters
- Between 5 and 10 liters
- More than 10 liters
- I don't know / Don't remember

12. If a local used oil collection or recycling program existed, do you think the place where you work would participate?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

13. Based on your experience, what do you think kitchen staff usually believe about the consequences of pouring oil or grease down the drain or disposing of it improperly?

(You can select multiple options.)

- That it pollutes water and harms the environment
- That it can cause pipe or drain blockages
- That it's harmless if done in small amounts
- That it's a common practice and not a big problem
- That it's prohibited or may result in penalties
- That it's not a topic people pay much attention to
- Other

14. Would you like to share any memory or experience you consider important about how oil or grease was handled in that place?

(For example: something that caught your attention, a common practice, a problem that occurred, or a solution they implemented.)

Supplementary Material

Results_Used_Oil_Survey

1. What is your age range?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
16–24 years	60.6
25–39 years	26.1
40–54 years	5.4
55 years or older	7.4
Prefer not to say	0.5
2. What is your gender identity?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Woman	54.2
Man	43.8
Prefer not to answer	2.0
3. What type of establishment have you worked in, currently work in, or are familiar with its kitchen operations?	Percentage based on the total number of selected responses
Restaurant	36.3
Fast food restaurant (e.g., McDonald's, KFC, Pollo Pepe, etc.)	13.7
Café	10.9
Diner / small local eatery	15.5
Street food stand	5.6
Other	18.0

4. Which of the following best describes your situation regarding kitchen work and the management of oil or grease waste? (Select one option.)	Percentage based on the total number of selected responses
I currently work in a kitchen and know how oil or grease waste is handled	19.7
I worked in a kitchen and know how this waste is managed	40.9
I have not worked directly in a kitchen, but I know how this waste is handled	28.4
I have no experience or knowledge on this topic	11.1
5. In which municipality is (or was) the establishment located where you work(ed) or know its kitchen operations?	Percentage based on the total number of selected responses
Guadalajara	44.0
Zapopan	12.9
Another municipality in the Metropolitan Area of Guadalajara	7.8
Another municipality in Jalisco different from the above	9.9
A state other than Jalisco	25.4
6. Did you receive any instruction or training on how to manage oil or grease waste in the kitchen of the establishment you know or where you worked/work?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Yes	33.0
No	57.6
I don't know / Don't remember	9.4
7. Was there any device or metal/plastic box under the sink to retain grease in the kitchen?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents

(Some places use grease traps to prevent oil and grease from reaching the drain.)	
Yes	48.0
No	40.6
I don't know / Didn't know what it was	11.4
8. How was oil or grease waste disposed of in the place where you work(ed) or know its operations? (You may select multiple options if applicable.)	Percentage based on the total number of selected responses
Stored in containers for collection	54.1
Left to cool and thrown in the trash	17.9
Poured directly down the drain	11.4
Not handled properly	10.0
I don't know / Don't remember	6.6
9. Do you know if an external company collected the used oil or cleaned the grease trap in the establishment?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Yes	35.0
No	40.9
I don't know	24.1
10. How many times was the frying oil reused before being discarded?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Only once	17.2
2 to 3 times	33.0
Until it changed color/texture	30.0
It was not reused	10.3

I don't know	9.4
11. Approximately how many liters of used oil were generated per week at the place where you work(ed) or know its operations?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Less than 5 liters	25.1
Between 5 and 10 liters	27.6
More than 10 liters	29.6
I don't know / Don't remember	17.7
12. If a local used oil collection or recycling program existed, do you think the place where you work would participate?	Percentage based on the total number of respondents
Yes	54.2
No	17.2
I don't know	28.6
13. Based on your experience, what do you think kitchen staff usually believe about the consequences of pouring oil or grease down the drain or disposing of it improperly? (You can select multiple options.)	Percentage based on the total number of selected responses
That it pollutes water and harms the environment	23.4
That it can cause pipe or drain blockages	25.1
That it's harmless if done in small amounts	15.0
That it's a common practice and not a big problem	10.3
That it's prohibited or may result in penalties	7.5
That it's not a topic people pay much attention to	16.2
Other	2.6